

Deliverable D6.10.

Pilot Mammendorf (CSI) Technical report and achieved results (2 | 2)

Deliverable report

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DIGIECOQUARRY project is fully concerned about the potential social risks that may arise as a consequence of the project's activities. For this reason, a dedicated Work Package (**WP7 - Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policymakers**) is active since the beginning of the project identifying, analysing and monitoring social risks in each of the project sites. Main social risks have been already analysed and classified in deliverables 7.1 and 7.2, including also potential risks of DIGIECOQUARRY technologies' deployment beyond the end of the project. The identification and classification of social risks allow **a close follow-up of the main potential negative impacts in society to avoid them throughout the whole project activities**. Among potential social risks, the impact on the workforce is monitored with specific attention to ensure full adaptation of workers to new working technologies and processes and avoid job destruction.

To ensure a successful implementation of the developed technologies in the pilot sites, social risks identified in WP7 for each pilot have been carefully considered. WP6 also includes the assessment and monitoring of relevant KPIs, which will help reduce the risk of work accidents and minimize the environmental impact.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
3D	three-dimensional
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
BIM	Building Information Modelling
D (number)	Deliverable (number of deliverable)
DEQ	DIGIECOQUARRY
GA	Grant Agreement
GPS	Global Positioning System
H&S	Health and Safety
IQS	Intelligent Quarrying system
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KTA	Key Technology Area
RTK	Real-Time Kinematic
WP	Work Package
Unit	Description
km/ m / mm	kilometre / meter / millimetre
ltr.	litre
rpm	revolutions per minute
t /kg /g /µg	ton / kilogram / gram /microgram
a / h / min / s or (sec)	year / hour / minute / second

1 Pilot overview

The quarry Mammendorf run by CSI is located around 20 km west of Magdeburg in Germany. The hard rock quarry produces high quality Andesit products that are used in several applications in the asphalt, concrete and construction industry.

Figure 1 Drone image of the treatment plant in the quarry Mammendorf.

At the beginning of the production process the blasted rock is hauled to the pre-crusher with dump trucks. The crushed rock is stored on a large buffer stockpile. During the following process the material is crushed and screened multiple times to produce the high-quality aggregate fractions needed. The treatment plant and parts of the quarry are shown in Figure 1.

In detail the quarry side consists of the following main areas:

- Mining areas with four to five benches.
- Overburden and topsoil removal on the upper benches.
- Dump side for overburden and waste material.
- Pre-crusher and buffer stockpile.
- The treatment plant for secondary and tertiary crushing, screening and direct loading.
- Multiple stockpile areas for separated storage of the finished fractions (products).
- Infrastructure area with offices, plant control, workshop, truck scale, fuel station and parking location.

An overview of the whole pilot quarry with a description of the main areas is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Overview of the whole quarry Mammendorf with short site description

The main DEQ subject targeted in the pilot Mammendorf is the management, data recording and process evaluation of the mobile fleet used for mining, overburden removal, dumping and product loading. The quarry is the reference pilot for mobile machinery and its more efficient use and reduction of emissions.

The main KPIs for the pilot Mammendorf are the minimisation of transport distances, the reduction of fuel-consumption, CO² emissions as well as downtime and repairs.

The Mammendorf pilot site is thereby connected to the following activities defined in the GA:

- Mobile equipment digitalisation using special HW.
- Mobile data collection, transmission and process evaluation using developed SW solutions.
- Novel geofence system for material tracking.
- Near-real time process modelling.
- Data integration in the BIM and IQS.

- Development of artificial intelligence algorithms.
- Environmental simulations platform.
- Social acceptance and communication with policy members.

The main work of the CSI-team has been in WP6 T6.4 (pilot implementation at CSIs quarry) but relates to WP3 T3.4 including the installations of data loggers in the mixed OEM mobile quarry equipment (wheel loaders, dump and road trucks and excavators), if necessary, the installation of a RTK-system, and the set-up of a geofence system for material tracking. The data from the data logger is used to evaluate central KPIs from the mobile fleet including for example fuel consumption, working and idling times and technical alerts. The KPIs are displayed in the DH&P expert system that functions as fleet management system. Based on that the general processes are validated, further KPIs are analysed and process optimization KPIs can be conducted by the quarry staff. The target is to minimise fuel consumption, improve equipment efficiency, minimise idle- and downtimes and improve the internal road conditions as well as H&S measures. All activities described are related to KTA 3.3.

The further activities for the general data integration on BIM, AI and IQS level are related to KTA 4.1, KTA 4.2 and KTA 4.3. The environmental simulation platform to be set up for Mammendorf is developed following KTA 6.1. The Social and communication targets are developed in KSA 7.1 and KSA 8.1.

It is important to mention that deliverable D6.4 will be taken as a reference together with the deliverables of WP3 and WP4 in order not to repeat unnecessarily content.

2 Implementation of technologies

2.1 Development and Installation of the Data Logger (T3.4.1)

The specifications for the universal data logger have been defined between CSI, DH&P and the hardware manufacturer in order to fulfil the needs of the demanding and harsh quarry environment. The logger must be compatible with different OEM CAN-BUS Systems and interfaces. The data transmission must be reliable and internal storage capacity must be sufficient to bridge times of reduced network availability. For data transmission different options including the option of an on-side buffer server have been evaluated. WLAN, Bluetooth and Mobile Communication (GSM) must be covered from the data logger to allow a broad spectrum of data transmission and sensor connection technologies. The logger must be equipped with internal power supply to be able to record positions or transmit data even if the machine is turned off. As the position of the mobile machines is essential for almost every target KPI, the GPS module of the logger must have the ability to be optionally equipped with RTK capabilities including the connection to an external reference station. The logger must be dust and water protected and show a high durability from heat, cold and vibrations. The different functions of the data logger are explained in the deliverable D3.8 of WP3. The logger was tested in a different CSI quarry for 3 weeks in order to fulfil the defined requirements and pre-test possible installation positions and issues.

The Mammendorf quarry fleet consists of the following machines to be equipped with the data logger in the DEQ project when M3.3 (final installation and IQS integration) is completed in M36. As indicated the first mobile machines were already equipped in the first installation phase before M3.1 (Mobile Machinery sensors ready for 1st implementation campaign in the pilots (prototypes)) in M25. The other machines were equipped in the second installation phase.

Dump Trucks / Road Trucks

- Used for material hauling of blasted rock, overburden, fines and products.
- 4 Caterpillar 775G dump trucks built between 2015 – 2022 (1 dump truck equipped in the 1st installation stage).
- 1 Komatsu HD325 dump truck built 2022.
- 2 Volvo FMX 500 four-axel trucks built 2022 (1 truck equipped in the 1st installation stage).

Excavators

- Used for loading of blasted rock or overburden materials.
- 2 Caterpillar 374 NG/FL built 2020 and 2022 (1 excavator equipped in the 1st installation stage) – in 10/2024 the FL was replaced by another NG.
- 1 Caterpillar 352F XE built 2017.
- 1 Caterpillar 329 FL built 2015.

Wheel-Loaders

- Used for loading of products to customers, fines and auxiliary work.
- 3 Caterpillar 972 M XE built between 2015 and 2021.
- 1 Komatsu WA 475 built 2020 (equipped in the 1st installation stage).

The installation was divided into two stages. In the first stage several problems came up with the CAN Bus connection when installing the data logger. That issue was solved with technicians on site or in contact to the OEMs. Based on this experience the complete fleet was equipped in a second stage. The installation positions on the four machines of the stage 1 installation are given in the following figures. On all other machines the installations are very similar.

Figure 3 Dump Truck (Caterpillar 775G) with installed data logger.

Figure 4 Truck (Volvo FMX 500) with installed data logger.

Figure 5 Excavator (Caterpillar 374) with installed data logger.

Figure 6 Wheel Loader (Komatsu WA 475) with installed data logger.

Due to the sufficient mobile network connection in the quarry the installed on-side buffer server has not been needed. The data from the installed data loggers is transferred via a mobile network connection directly to the buffer server of the hardware manufacturer. From there the data is transferred via an API directly to the DH&P AutoPLAN expert system.

2.2 Development and Configuration of Software (T3.4.1)

The AutoPLAN expert system is structured in the user frontend including visual mapping and dashboard functions and the raw data background handling where the incoming data from the mobile machines is managed. The incoming raw data is hereby parameterized and stored in a SQL database.

After accessing the DH&P AutoPLAN expert system the user can access the following main functions. There are many functions of the AutoPLAN expert system that will not be used or further developed in the DEQ project. Those functions are neglected and not further described in this deliverable.

- Mapping tool for visualisation of any geodata including digital orthophotos and topographical information showing machine activity and track visualisation including visualisation of the defined 3D-geofences, vehicle speed and altitude profiles.
- Display of all raw data sets recorded for each mobile machine including comparison of data sets and graph visualisation to manually analyse errors; check function to see available data sets stored for each machine and to quickly identify missing data (data gaps).
- Dashboards for the plant and each machine to be used by the quarry staff to show defined KPIs calculated from the machine and additional plant data for verification.

The raw data management tool is used to visualise and compare the raw unprocessed data recorded from each machine with the installed data logger. It also shows how many data sets are available for each machine on a single day, week or month. All raw data can be visualised in different graphic representations. Figure 7 shows the raw data management tool with an overview about the different values and timestamps.

Figure 7 Raw data tool for visualisation and data comparison and the number of available data sets.

Figure 9 single KPI overview and calculation (here fuel consumption).

From the raw data the defined KPIs regarding fuel consumption, mass movement, drive tracks and material tracking are calculated. The KPIs can be accessed and evaluated using the single KPI overview shown in Figure 9.

The KPIs are presented to the plant staff in dashboards to give a fast and structured overview of the overall fleet performance and the relevant indicators across machines from different manufactures/brands.

2.3 Interfaces to Fuel Station, Belt Scale System and Tire Pressure Monitoring System (T3.4.1)

For validation of the recorded mobile data, interfaces to the existing technology for automated data recording are established to be integrated in the expert system. This includes the integration of the main belt-scales installed right after the pre-crusher and the refuelling and documentation software that integrates data from the fixed fuel station and the mobile fuel truck equipped with the same system. For both data sources APIs or/and manual input functions are integrated into the expert system. The data are used to validate and supplement the data gathered from the mobile machines.

The belt scales 1.21 and 1.23 to be integrated are installed behind the pre-crusher and at the belt for the separated fines. The accumulated values of both scales give the total daily gross production transported to and dumped into the pre-crusher. Both belt scales are of a similar type/build. The software will query the production in tons and give an overview about the daily, weekly, monthly accumulated production and pre-screen-material. The installed belt scale 1.21 just after the pre crusher is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10 Installation position of the belt scale 1.21 behind the pre-crusher.

The fuel used for all mobile machines is either tanked from the fixed fuel station next to the plant or from the mobile fuel truck. Both fuel station and fuel truck are equipped with a fuel management software that records all fuel data. For this purpose, all employees running mobile machinery at the quarry have a vehicle specific fuel chip that has to be used for each refuelling process. Before the refuelling process can be started the chips need to be placed on the chip reader at both fuel stations and the odometer (km) or the current engine hours (h) need to be entered. For each machine in the quarry the total amount of fuel tanked for each refilling process as well as accumulated values and the engine hours or the driven kilometres are exchanged for validation via the developed API with the expert system. The expert system automatically validates the KPIs calculated from the recorded mobile machinery data with the data exchanged from the belt scales and the fuel management software.

The fixed fuel station and the mobile fuel truck as well as the installed chip readers are shown in Figure 11.

Date	Asset	Fuelstation	Working Hours [h]	Mileage [km]	Amount [l]	Fuel	Worker	Remark
3/1/2024 9:08 AM	CAT 775G-3	Tankstation	1843		716.00	Diesel	Amelungen	
3/1/2024 11:34 AM	CAT 972-3	Tankstation	7448		226.04	Diesel	Manolache	
3/1/2024 11:46 AM	CAT 972-2	Tankstation	7825		169.79	Diesel	Pelzelt, Dirk	
3/1/2024 12:44 PM	CAT 374-2	Tankstation	2030		546.21	Diesel	Schomburg	
3/1/2024 2:36 PM	CAT 352F XE	Tankstation	8155		339.11	Diesel	Schomburg	
3/1/2024 11:32 PM	CAT 972-1	Tankstation	17254		209.14	Diesel	Löbke	
3/2/2024 8:36 AM	CAT 972-2	Tankstation	7837		176.00	Diesel	Pelzelt, Dirk	
3/2/2024 10:54 AM	CAT 972-3	Tankstation	7457		180.10	Diesel	Manolache	
3/4/2024 12:40 PM	CAT 374-2	Tankstation	2042		424.20	Diesel	Schomburg	
3/4/2024 1:34 PM	CAT 775G-1	Tankstation	13441		680.15	Diesel	Kunert	
3/4/2024 1:52 PM	HD 325	Tankstation	1670		249.33	Diesel	Bujdzak	
3/4/2024 3:14 PM	CAT 352F XE	Tankstation	8161		142.65	Diesel	Schomburg	
3/4/2024 8:10 PM	CAT 329	Tankstation	11648		300.62	Diesel	Schomburg	
3/5/2024 12:22 AM	CAT 775G-3	Tankstation	1866		712.02	Diesel	Amelungen	
3/5/2024 11:22 AM	CAT 972-3	Tankstation	7489		179.74	Diesel	Pelzelt, Dirk	
3/5/2024 1:00 PM	CAT 374-2	Tankstation	2054		475.46	Diesel	Schomburg	
3/5/2024 1:16 PM	HD 325	Tankstation	1684		304.30	Diesel	Bujdzak	
3/5/2024 4:10 PM	CAT 972-2	Tankstation	8174		321.10	Diesel	Schomburg	
3/5/2024 4:54 PM	CAT 972-2	Tankstation	7950		225.12	Diesel	Jäger	
3/6/2024 5:08 AM	CAT 972-2	Tankstation	7958		150.07	Diesel	Manolache	
3/6/2024 11:48 AM	CAT 972-3	Tankstation	7480		174.57	Diesel	Pelzelt, Dirk	
3/6/2024 2:22 PM	CAT 352F XE	Tankstation	8184		292.12	Diesel	Schomburg	
3/6/2024 6:48 PM	HD 325	Tankstation	1696		216.03	Diesel	Bombach	
3/6/2024 7:04 PM	CAT 972-2	Tankstation	7965		65.03	Diesel	Jäger	
3/7/2024 4:28 AM	CAT 972-2	Tankstation	7973		137.03	Diesel	Manolache	
3/7/2024 11:34 AM	CAT 972-3	Tankstation	7491		175.05	Diesel	Pelzelt, Dirk	
3/7/2024 12:46 PM	CAT 374-2	Tankstation	2068		486.92	Diesel	Schomburg	
3/7/2024 1:08 PM	HD 325	Tankstation	1710		296.96	Diesel	Albrecht	
3/7/2024 2:34 PM	CAT 352F XE	Tankstation	8197		320.90	Diesel	Schomburg	
3/7/2024 4:52 PM	CAT 972-2	Tankstation	7980		95.06	Diesel	Jäger	
3/8/2024 1:10 AM	CAT 775G-2	Tankstation	17848		727.05	Diesel	Schomburg	
3/8/2024 2:50 AM	CAT 775G-3	Tankstation	1888		727.02	Diesel	Amelungen	
3/8/2024 5:00 AM	CAT 972-2	Tankstation	7988		111.13	Diesel	Bujdzak	
3/8/2024 11:10 AM	CAT 972-3	Tankstation	7500		115.20	Diesel	Pelzelt, Dirk	
3/8/2024 4:44 PM	HD 325	Tankstation	1719		160.05	Diesel	Bombach	
3/8/2024 4:54 PM	CAT 972-2	Tankstation	7992		65.72	Diesel	Jäger	
3/8/2024 9:20 PM	CAT 352F XE	Tankstation	8208		274.91	Diesel	Städler	
3/9/2024 8:46 AM	CAT 972-3	Tankstation	7510		150.07	Diesel	Pelzelt, Dirk	
3/9/2024 4:14 PM	HD 325	Tankstation	1728		254.95	Diesel	Bombach	

Figure 11 Fixed fuel station (left) and mobile fuel station (upper right and chip reader (lower right) and refuelling data.

Integration of Tire Pressure Monitoring System

Some of the mobile machinery is additionally equipped with non-OEM external sensors. In case of CSI all wheeled machines are equipped with tire-pressure-monitoring systems (TPMS) (see Figure 12). These systems consist of sensors on each wheel, measuring the pressure and the temperature inside the tire and sending it via radio-signal to a control-unit inside the cabin. All data is displayed on that unit. The progress of temperature and pressure is stored in an internal storage. In case of low- or high-pressure or overtemperature, the system is creating an alert. As tire-pressure is a very important factor to operate a machine in a safe and efficient way, it was planned to connect the TPMS-systems to the data-logger and transfer the data to the platform. However, numerous attempts to contact the manufacturer and harmonise the interfaces have failed. As a result, it has not yet been possible to save this sensor data in the data logger and make it available in the system.

Figure 12 The Sensor and Display of the installed tire-pressure-monitoring-system.

Some of the wheel loaders at CSI are equipped with non-OEM-weight-scales. The reason is that most OEM-weighbridges are not calibrated legally for trade purposes. The non-OEM-weight-scales monitor and store all material-movements of the machine. For the mass-flow-recording and to determine and optimise the efficiency of the machine, this data is mandatory. The weight-information must be connected to the GPS-data and the geofencing, to be part of the mass-flow-capturing. The display of the external weighting system on a wheel loader is shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13 The external weight scale on a wheel loader and the signal data in AutoPLAN.

2.4 Development of the Geofence-System (T3.4.2)

The 3D-Geofence-System is based on the current topographical model to show the current quarry layout and different operation areas, which is quickly changing due to the high production rates of the quarry. A high-quality drone flight and the photogrammetric visualisation of the quarry in a 3D point cloud was conducted for Mammendorf during the DEQ project (see Figure 14).

Figure 14 Screenshot from the high-resolution point cloud used for developing the topographical model

Based on the topographical models and all areas source or target for material transport a 3D-geofence structure has been established for material tracking and activity detection (see Figure 15). This model differs mainly between overburden removal and rock extraction as well as stockpile areas and must be updated at regular intervals (1 to 2 times per year).

Figure 15 Temporary geofence structure for the quarry CSI

2.5 Platform design implementation (Task 4.2)

The ICT platform in fact is not specific to a given quarry. In D4.2, titled “Report on IQS Design and Architecture,” the design and architecture of the Intelligent Quarrying System (IQS), developed by AKKODIS, are described. The implementation of this architecture and site’s specific development were described in D4.6 “Report on IQS, Services Integration and deployment”. Hence, more details could be found as follow:

- The IQS components currently deployed, their main functions and availability for each pilot site are described in section 3.1 of D4.3
- The Centralized data management platform and the CDMP front-end are described in section 3.2 of D4.3
- Transport service, Plant production service, Environmental data management service, Health and safety service are described in section 3.2.3 of D4.6
- Business management tools Section 3.4 of D4.6
- The data lake, the databases, the IoT platform and Talend integration are described respectively in section 3.2.4, 3.2.5, 3.2.6 and 3.2.7 of D4.6
- The data connectors are described in section 3.3 of D4.6

The following 2 figures show the front-end welcome page and the Shared data screen created for CSI.

Figure 16 CDMP Front-End: Welcome page – “Home” screen and “Shared Data” screen

Several quarry processes (Transport, Environment) have been implemented within the IQS, and their data models have been defined. Connections using REST APIs have been created, enabling direct communication for data exchange between the expert systems and the IQS according to a newly defined common data format.

The data integration process has been implemented, with data flowing at varying frequencies (hourly, daily, monthly) based on the use case. Integration was achieved using a proxy design pattern, adopted by all site data providers, to push data from SmartQuarry (DH&P) and PlantSmith systems to the IQS, and to enable data consumers to pull data from the IQS.

The results list of the IQS data integration within the project, including the data availability status in the data lake across all sites, is detailed in Section 4 of D4.6.

In addition to the reporting tools provided by the expert systems, the IQS leveraged the Power BI ecosystem to create comprehensive dashboards and reports that provide insights into KPIs from different facets of quarrying. These tools break down data silos and facilitate data integration from diverse sources, enhancing decision-making capabilities and performance monitoring. The dashboards are described in section 4.3 of D4.2 and in section 3 of D4.6.

All the dashboards created for CSI are accessible in one power-bi application accessible to pilot site's users as shown in next figure.

Figure 17 DEQ Power BI App for CSI

Processing and storing raw data in a relational database like Postgres proved inefficient, taking hours for storage and extraction. To address this, a new solution was needed to achieve data storage within 15 minutes and consultation under a minute, while allowing flexible data analysis, parameter correlations, and customizable dashboards at low cost. The TICK Stack (Telegraf, InfluxDB, Chronograf, and Kapacitor) was selected for its suitability with time-series data, along with Grafana for dashboard creation. The new IQS data flow integrates these tools, with raw data converted into InfluxDB format by the DHP Raw Data service and visualized through Grafana dashboards. The following figure shows how this new solution (Tick Stack) is integrated with the IQS/CDMP platform. More details can be found in section 3.2.3 in D 4.6.

Figure 18 IQS updated data Flow integrating the Tick Stack

With this new solution, a data exploration environment is created that enables the creation of global dashboards. As an example, in Figure 16, this dashboard displays a map with truck positions, hourly engine RPM, engine RPM, and fuel usage for the same reporting period (time range).

Figure 19 Grafana dashboard example with Engine RPM, Fuel usage, Truck tracking

2.6 AI algorithms (Task 4.3)

The AI services designed in the project are summarised in the following table mentioning the pilot quarry they belong to:

AI Service Area	Pilot site	SIGMA	UPM-AI
Hawkeye (CV) COLORIMETRY (QUAL)	CEMEX	X	X
Hawkeye (CV) GRAIN SIZE	CEMEX	X	X
Stock Forecast (CV) STOCKPILE VOLUME	Holcim & Vicat	X	X
Predictive Maintenance (PrMa) - ANOMALIES DETECTION (Acoustic & video &...)	CSI	X	X
Metaquarry (Document Mgt)	Holcim & Vicat	X	
Consumptions & production forecast	CIMPOR	X	X

Only the ones about CSI Mammendorf's quarry are described in this deliverable.

It is important to mention that the deliverable D 4.3, "Report on the AI Algorithms and Services," contains detailed design specifications, and the contents here are, in some cases, a summary of the text in the deliverable.

For CSI, the AI service developed is related to predictive maintenance and detecting anomalies or failures. This AI service measures the sound and vibration profiles of given equipment to categorize the sample obtained as exclusively belonging to that type of equipment. For CSI, it is planned to monitor a cone crusher from Sandvick.

Failure and anomalies detection AI service

The service aims to use aerial and contact sensors to monitor the production line at the quarry site constantly. Continuous monitoring of the different lines and components should ease the detection of machinery malfunctions or failures and minimise their impact on production. Ultimately, this may be used to develop predictive maintenance capabilities using external metadata on the individual parts involved.

Microphones and vibration sensors are used to monitor the plant and collect data from the different parts in production. In particular, the service evaluates screens, crushers, and conveyor belts. Acoustic anomalies are known to be good predictors of the functioning condition of these parts. They are widely used by plant operators to detect abnormal functioning and to diagnose upcoming difficulties. As operators are not all equally trained, their perception degrades with time, they do not remember complex patterns easily, and they cannot sit at all points in the plant and monitor all its parts at a time; the service aims to expand their capabilities. By locating sensors at defined locations in the production plant and continuously monitoring sounds, noises, and vibrations, the aim is:

- Collecting audio data representing normal plant operations and (if possible) abnormal patterns. The initial dataset can be collected from instrumentation components or (preferably) directly from the same infrastructure used in monitoring.
- Training light models to trigger alarms when abnormal patterns or deviations are detected. Typically, the first will relate to malfunctions or failures, and the second to early degradation patterns that may be used for effective predictive maintenance,
- Uploading and running these models onto low-cost sensors located at the production line,
- Continuously and automatically evaluating (classifying) input audio stream events to detect abnormal ones.
- Detecting and storing audio stream fragments that represent abnormal patterns and store them. Submitting these fragments to the cloud infrastructure for evaluation and possible model retraining.
- Training advanced models on cloud infrastructure to validate triggers and classify events.
- Pushing alarms onto the plant information/alarm system, dashboards, and DEQ data infrastructure. Historical records on these events shall be used to develop predictive maintenance capabilities that may expand this service.

General Summary

Section	Description
Service Name	Failure Detection Service
Overview	<p>This service aims to constantly monitor the production line at the quarry site using aerial and contact sensors. Continuous monitoring of the different lines and components should ease the detection of machinery malfunctions or failures and minimise their impact on production. Ultimately, this may be used to develop predictive and prospective maintenance capabilities using external and historical metadata on the individual parts involved.</p> <p>The service uses a two-stage platform involving a relatively small intelligent capturing device (edge) with a microprocessor and various sensors, particularly microphones and vibration sensors, to monitor a given quarry plant component (conveyor belt, crusher, sieve, etc.) and collect data that AI models process (on edge and cloud) to characterise the equipment under test and detect failures.</p>
Key Components	<p>The service requires a specific hardware component to capture noise and vibrations at the quarry's, monitor specific equipment's functioning, and generate functioning profiles and alarms. Deliverable D4.3 introduced the architecture of this device, based on a Raspberry Pi:</p> <p><i>Figure 20. HW of the deployed sensors and schematic on the main software components focusing on control.</i></p>
	<p>This device must be placed near the device under test and have access to an AC power connection outlet. Conducted tests only included one single device. However, multiple devices can be placed in a single quarry site to address different components and build up a broader sound and vibration image of the site. The edge components act as early processors of real-time audio and vibrations. This component first detects detected anomalies or spurious patterns. The cloud systems coordinate the monitoring process, managing the edge components, controlling the models, and integrating the input data. Alarms are processed at the back-end side to classify them (if possible) and train models.</p> <p>For data communication purposes (i.e., data exchange, command and control), a VPN must be deployed using a wired connection or a Wi-Fi network, for example, as needed by the CSI where the service is being deployed.</p>

	<p>The amount of data to be processed is significant, and the solution must operate in real-time on all connected devices. The edge modules filter out most of the standard (non-relevant) data, allowing the service to focus on the spurious patterns.</p> <p>The models' training runs online and/or offline based on the data collected in normal conditions (to avoid exchange with the cloud infrastructure) and the possibly abnormal patterns (evaluated as possible alarms on the edge side and finally processed on the cloud infrastructure).</p> <p>Following the proposed two-stage, edge-to-cloud structure, data storage is primarily minimised. For the models to run on an edge device in real-time, they must be light and efficient. We use optimised (quantized) models and a purpose-specific processor. We must restrict the collected data to less than 100 GB at the edge. The cloud servers must handle more significant amounts of data and larger models. The former is used to extend or retrain future models, and the latter is used to classify the abnormal patterns and launch the alarms. AI models must run on both sides of the system, and the differences between the models are very significant in complexity and size.</p>
Target Audience	<p>This device is usable in a wide range of industry applications characterised by noisy and heavy-duty machines. Managers and operators are targeted in quarries, but any plant manager is also targeted. For example, fabrication processes involve heavy equipment that is not equipped with sensors that monitor its performance.</p> <p>We include data centres among other application scenarios we have considered.</p>
Hardware Requirements	<p>The edge device(s): As previously described, if various are installed, they must all be virtually connected to the same network. The VPN connects them with the out-of-premise cloud infrastructure. The individual edge modules fire their alarms. The cloud modules deliver accurate labelling of the alarms, firing these to the external information services (DEQ Data Lake).</p> <p>Local network connectivity: from the edge component to the network. Alternatively, the system is devised to avoid needing such components using 4G connectivity.</p> <p>Virtual network control connects the individual components with the cloud servers. The service is designed not to require this connection to be operative all day but largely recommends that it happen and that we keep track of it.</p> <p>Cloud servers: The whole service is managed by external servers that monitor the individual edge components to which these connect. Those serve the pre-filtered data or get their models updated from the cloud side. Processed and tagged alarms are fired from this specific component.</p>
Installation Process	<p>Edge modules must be placed at the quarry site. They can be easily attached to metal structures. They must be powered by an external current and connected to a network. The current design requires Ethernet or Wi-Fi connectivity, though 4G connectivity may also be allowed in future designs.</p> <p>Once it is plugged in, the system has to be started. Once the HW is activated, the internal processor will attempt connectivity through the VPN directly with the external servers. As soon as this is achieved,</p> <p>If this connection is not completed, the system can still run, operating on one of the following modes:</p> <p>(0) Collect new records to build a suitable model. Once this is completed the module will communicate (if possible) the model with the cloud system, along with any possible anomalies it may detect.</p> <p>(1) Run a preloaded anomaly detection model. The system will store and communicate (if possible) any anomalies it detects. If the module finds systematic anomalies, it will start mode (0) if and only if it was marked from the cloud servers or if the system is operating autonomously, lacking an open connection with the master.</p>

	Active and linked edge components are controlled from the cloud and can be validated in real time.
Communication Protocols -	<p>The service edge components require Wi-Fi or Ethernet connectivity. The following designs may as well operate on 5G. However, the models operating on these components will typically require rapid retraining and adaptation of the anomaly-detection modules. Therefore, it is worth a rapid link.</p> <p>The device can send data to the IQS cloud infrastructure and servers. VPN connectivity is mandatory for command and control.</p>
Data Storage & Management	<p>The device stores the running models and recent data locally (up to 1 GB) but typically sends the recorded data to a server in the cloud—both the edge and cloud components—to run AI algorithms. The device is autonomous and can be monitored remotely. To operate autonomously, it stores both local sensor data and service logs. The latter includes the anomaly detection results and the management of the edge and cloud models (updating, training, etc.).</p> <p>Backups run directly on the edge components, while the cloud service keeps backup on the models trained and deployed, the alarms generated, and the outputs delivered.</p> <p>All communications from the edge component to the cloud are encrypted. The edge component</p> <p>This service's modules do not manage any personal or sensible data. Even if the modules are destroyed to extract the collected data or the deployed models, this information could not compromise the service or the owners' data. If requested, disk encryption could be introduced without damaging the service performance or operation in any way.</p>
AI Integration & Implementation	<p>At the quarry. Input streams (audio and vibration) are digitally filtered and adapted to mitigate the impact of spurious background effects. At the same time, fixed-duration signal chunks are extracted to evaluate AI triggers based on time-frequency representations.</p> <p>The AI triggers are based on light AI models that evaluate a given event's likelihood instead of standard triggers (e.g., single or double directional edges, intervals, logic, counters, etc.). For this project, we use unsupervised models trained on conventional, robust audio representations, avoiding the need for energy- and time-consuming computations. The edge module manages the models while trained and uploaded from the cloud. Multiple models can be used simultaneously and stored within the edge components. The command and control and service monitoring components handle execution control and monitoring, allowing the edge modules to operate autonomously or in connection with the cloud server whenever possible.</p> <p>Depending on the trigger's result, the system may extract the audio from the original sample and the compact triggering representation and share it with the IQS platform and the cloud back-end. This may happen in arbitrary situations, such as collecting probes to calibrate and monitor the system or when a trigger condition is met.</p> <p>If a trigger condition is met, different pieces of information are sent. The module shall:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fire an alarm to the alarm dashboard system (installed at the quarry). • Send an abnormal event to the IQS platform, including the type of event, timestamp, module/site unique identifier, and the corresponding raw signal to ease posterior processing. Note that for this task, a minimum delay may exist for the signalled alarm due to signal windowing and overlaps. • Send the data to the cloud module for storing and posterior evaluation of the sample using more advanced (and computationally heavier) models. These models may also validate the alarm using advanced AI audio models, categorising the event in an informed way. Additionally, the cloud

	<p>modules may find relevant information by integrating the information from multiple sensors. This holistic approach shall provide a more complete perspective on the quarry operations.</p> <p>The edge component includes minimum necessary functionalities to monitor its service, connectivity, health, etc., and allows full remote command and control. Regarding communications, the edge component is intended to include different RF front-ends, typically Wi-Fi, 3G, and 4G, and a physical connection through Ethernet RJ45. The processor Linux-based operating system manages all these interfaces seamlessly for the rest of the components.</p> <p>At the Service back-end in the cloud, this component is meant to communicate with all deployed edge modules from the different quarry sites and to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Merge results and metadata. • Monitor the service, including health checks on all its components. • Monitor and control the learning process and model deployment on the edge components. • Orchestrate operations among all edge components. • Manage data, control and track operations, and store the extracted input data. • Export results to the DEQ infrastructure: IQS. <p>Additionally, the back-end must also:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Control the models' training process for the edge components. • Train its models for anomalous event classification.
<p>Application Features</p>	<p>The Core functionalities of the AI-powered application include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seamless connection of the HW device at the quarry site • Seamless integration of the node on the Service System • AI triggering of events from the deployed edge devices • AI processing of events to produce categorised alarms from the cloud side • Seamless calibration of the acoustic and vibration models • Seamless learning and detection of abnormal patterns. <p>Regarding the user interface and user experience design considerations, the service only requires a simple front-end for presenting detected events, tracking historical data, and controlling fixed alarms. Dashboards installed at quarry sites may include all these functionalities.</p> <p>Below is a visualisation of the dashboard that was designed.</p>

	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Location 1</th> <th>Location 2</th> <th>Location 3</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Alarms validated</td> <td>103 85%</td> <td>45 93%</td> <td>- pending</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Latest since last</td> <td>23.01.2024 +105 days</td> <td>13.02.2024 +8 hours</td> <td>- pending</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Alive Last mssg</td> <td>56 days +15min</td> <td>24 hours +1 hour</td> <td>- pending</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Location 1	Location 2	Location 3	Alarms validated	103 85%	45 93%	- pending	Latest since last	23.01.2024 +105 days	13.02.2024 +8 hours	- pending	Alive Last mssg	56 days +15min	24 hours +1 hour	- pending
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<p>Security & Compliance</p>	<p>Cybersecurity measures to protect hardware and data include strong access controls with unique user IDs and multi-factor authentication. Tamper-evident seals are introduced to detect physical intrusion attempts, and storage data is encrypted outside the processor. Virtual private networks (VPNs) are used for secure remote access. Otherwise, no connection from the network is allowed.</p> <p>Regular security audits and updates, including periodic vulnerability assessments and penetration testing, will be conducted to keep all software and firmware up to date with the latest security patches. A comprehensive incident response plan will be developed and regularly tested to ensure timely reporting and addressing of security incidents.</p> <p>For GDPR compliance, data minimization practices are implemented, collecting only necessary information, even in this application involving no critical or personal data. Detailed logs of data processing activities are maintained, and regular data protection impact assessments are conducted, both on the server side and the remote devices. Secure methods like append-only logs are used to ensure tamper-proof storage of records, and automated alerts are set up for unusual activity or potential breaches.</p> <p>Employees will receive regular training on compliance requirements and best practices. All vendors and partners handling system data will be ensured to comply with relevant regulations, and third-party security practices and data handling procedures are regularly audited.</p>																
<p>Performance Metrics</p>	<p>Edge AI performance</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Trigger Accuracy Rate: Measures unsupervised models' ability to distinguish true anomalies from background noise. Computed on external tests on calibrated models. Computation: $(\text{Validated triggers by cloud AI}) / (\text{Total triggers sent}) \times 100$. Inference Latency: Critical for real-time safety/operational events response. Computation: Time between signal chunk input and trigger decision output. Alarm Accuracy Rate: This rate evaluates the number of detected events and those regarded as abnormal by quarry operators. This figure balances safety (minimizing missed events) vs. operational disruption (reducing false alarms). Computation: Compared against cloud AI's validation results. 																

	<p>Data Processing Metrics</p> <p>4. Chunk Processing Time. Ensures fixed-duration signal windows meet real-time requirements. Computation: Average time to filter/extract time-frequency representations per chunk.</p> <p>5. Data Compression Ratio. Based on the triggering configuration, evaluate the bandwidth usage reduction for raw audio/vibration data transmission. Computation: (Compressed size) / (Original size).</p> <p>Communication Metrics</p> <p>6. Transmission Success Rate. Ensure reliable alarms/raw data delivery to the cloud/IQS platform. Computation: (Successfully transmitted packets) / (Total packets).</p> <p>7. Multi-Interface Uptime. Monitoring Wi-Fi, 4G, and Ethernet reliability for failover readiness. Computation: (Active interface time) / (Total monitored time).</p> <p>System Health Metrics</p> <p>8. Edge Module Resource Utilization. Prevent CPU/RAM bottlenecks in edge devices. Computation: Average % usage of CPU, RAM, and storage.</p> <p>9. Service Availability. Tracks uptime for edge/cloud components. Computation: (Operational time) / (Total time) × 100.</p> <p>Operational Metrics</p> <p>10. Alarm Response Time. Speed of quarry addressing triggered events. Computation: Time between alarm firing and presentation in the dashboard.</p> <p>11. Model Update Success Rate. Ensure seamless deployment of new AI models to edge devices. Computation: (Successful deployments) / (Total deployment attempts).</p>
Support & Maintenance	<p>Ongoing technical support:</p> <p>Quarry monitoring systems require continuous technical support to ensure optimal performance. A dedicated support team should be available 24/7 to resolve IT issues, minimising disruptions to operations. This support typically includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • On-site and remote assistance tailored to quarry industry needs. • Prompt resolution of hardware and software issues. • Regular system health checks and performance optimization. <p>Updates:</p> <p>Keeping the quarry monitoring system up to date is crucial for maintaining efficiency and security. Updates should include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regular updates on the AI models and periodic calibration. • Regular software patches to address bugs and vulnerabilities. • Firmware updates for hardware components.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Periodic upgrades to introduce new features and improve system capabilities. • Ensuring compatibility with evolving industry standards and regulations. <p>Troubleshooting:</p> <p>Effective troubleshooting procedures are essential for minimizing downtime and maintaining system reliability. Key aspects include:</p> <p>The service implements protocols to systematically identify and resolve issues quickly, including remote diagnostics. The system can detect inadequate service trends and decide on proactive correction actions, including network connectivity problems.</p> <p>Additionally, the service must provide operators with troubleshooting guides and training. After PoC, materials to present the service, frequent responses, and tutorials must be provided. The service will include a knowledge base of common issues and their solutions.</p> <p>Periodic sensor and device maintenance is required.</p>
<p>Business Model & Pricing</p>	<p>We established a subscription-based model.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Customer segments: The service is aimed at quarrying sites or other industrial environments that require process or environment monitoring, such as automotive or farming industries. 2. Value proposition: The innovation monitors parameters or processes that were not monitored before and unveils new information from the available data. 3. Channels: Direct sales via interviews of commercial teams with IT departments. UPM contacts in specialized forums and contacts from associations and workgroups, including those headed by ANEFA. Sigma’s web channel and commercial offices are in Madrid, London, and Miami. 4. Customer relationships: Personalized assistance fitting to customer’s needs. 5. Revenue streams: Initial installation fee (depending on the type and number of sensors needed) plus an annual data storage and processing services license fee. O&M fee. 6. Key resources: Human resources include field installers, data analysts, hardware specialists, IT personnel, and mining engineers. Computation resources include cloud storage and servers for data processing. 7. Key activities: Monitoring, data analysis, process improvement. 8. Key partners: Potentially with hardware providers for developing ad-hoc sensors. 9. Cost structure: Human resources for development, O&M resources, servers (storage and processing), sensor hardware, and marketing resources. <p>Given the complexity of technologies, commercial and technical management always go hand in hand when defining the sales strategy for commercializing a new product. The following revenue model is established as a guideline. However, it must be adjusted according to the knowledge acquired in the pilot and after a more in-depth market potential analysis.</p> <p>Furthermore, due to the open nature of the service, its cost will highly depend on the number of sensors deployed and the information that should be generated.</p> <p>Thus, the pricing of the service will account for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initial requirements analysis: interviews with the customer to determine service goals and hardware requirements: 1.000 - 2.000 €.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deployment fee: a fixed 2.000 € fee plus 500 € per sensor (the price might increase depending on the type of sensor). • Additional functionalities: 1.000 – 3.000 € each. • O&M fee: 3.000 € annually.
Competitive Advantage	<p>Sensors. The system is based on commercially available sensors and in-house developments. In both cases, affordability has been a priority, reducing the cost of adopting the service.</p> <p>Advanced Edge AI Capabilities. The system utilizes light AI models at the edge for real-time event detection and analysis. This approach allows faster response times and reduced data transmission, outperforming traditional trigger-based systems.</p> <p>Continuous Learning and Adaptation. The system's ability to update AI models from the cloud to the edge allows for continuous improvement and adaptation to changing quarry conditions, a feature not commonly found in traditional monitoring systems.</p> <p>Holistic Multi-Sensor Integration. Unlike competitors, this system integrates data from multiple sensors (audio and vibration) to comprehensively analyse quarry operations. This holistic approach offers a more complete perspective, enabling better decision-making.</p> <p>Adaptive Filtering Techniques. The system employs adaptive digital filtering to mitigate background noise, improving the accuracy of event detection in challenging quarry environments.</p> <p>Cloud-Edge Hybrid Architecture. Combining edge processing with cloud-based advanced analytics offers real-time responsiveness and in-depth analysis capabilities, providing a more versatile solution than purely edge-based or cloud-based competitors.</p> <p>Autonomous Operation. The edge modules can operate autonomously when cloud connectivity is unavailable, ensuring continuous monitoring even in locations with unreliable network access.</p> <p>Flexible Communications. With multiple RF front-ends (Wi-Fi, 3G, 4G) and Ethernet connectivity, the system offers more robust and flexible communication options than systems relying on a single method.</p> <p>Several competitors offer quarry monitoring solutions, each with unique technologies. Here's a comparison with the system described earlier:</p> <p>SiteHive. Hexanodes monitor surface water, vibration, dust, and noise. They follow a similar multi-sensor approach but focus on environmental factors rather than AI-driven event detection.</p> <p>Prylada's Industrial Noise Monitoring Solution uses an IoT Gateway with sensors to collect real-time noise data. It offers dynamic mode switching for energy-efficient monitoring.</p> <p>CESVA's Noise Platform. Online platform for real-time noise analysis from a network of sensors. Cost-effective TA120 sensors allow for multi-point monitoring.</p> <p>SoftdB's Watch™ Monitoring Station. A mobile station for noise and vibration monitoring. Provides automated alerts and customizable reports. Complies with stringent measurement standards. Watch™ offers mobile noise and vibration monitoring with automated alerts. Noise Radar™ uses 6 microphones for directional noise measurement and color-coded noise contours.</p> <p>Competitors could not accurately run in any possible acoustic condition or seamlessly calibrate their devices to be autonomously managed. While Prylada mentions some adaptive features, the extent of AI</p>

	integration for predictive analysis or advanced pattern recognition is not evident across all systems nor explicitly mentioned in any newsletter or released press note.
Future Enhancements	<p>AI modelling will undoubtedly improve as long as more data is captured. One of the critical factors in the first stage was the lack of data representing failures. Therefore, only abnormal situations can be detected at the moment. However, the models used still need to be able to categorize different equipment and the types of failures they may run into. Typically, those will have a sound and vibration profile that is very peculiar concerning the type of failures. This includes (i) capturing detailed sound and vibration profiles for different machinery and failure modes and (ii) expanding datasets to include rare or complex failure scenarios, enabling more robust anomaly detection.</p> <p>Furthermore, the current models detect abnormal situations but cannot classify failures. Planned improvements will enable AI systems to identify specific equipment types based on their unique operational profiles. This was possible from the records collected since the early tests were conducted. Additionally, we aim to categorize failures using advanced pattern recognition and connect them to actual causes of failure of diagnosed conditions in the machinery or the operations.</p> <p>The system aims to integrate predictive maintenance capabilities as an additional value. AI systems will evolve from reactive anomaly detection to predictive maintenance capabilities. This involves (0) collecting historical data on the plant and the components, (1) using machine learning algorithms to analyse historical sensor data and predict potential failures before they occur, and (2) providing actionable insights, such as the urgency of repairs and recommendations for maintenance scheduling.</p> <p>Finally, dynamic mode switching will be introduced to optimize power consumption during monitoring. This ensures that edge modules operate efficiently without compromising performance in remote quarry environments.</p>

Activities performed since November 2023:

Data capturing

Using the Zoom H8 device, we ran a campaign to collect data at the CSI Mammendorf site (Germany). To complement this information, we also collected audio records in several locations, including quarries in Spain and Sweden. Additionally, we have recorded sound and vibration data at ETSIT-UPM as a testbed for the system deployed. We monitored the server infrastructure being used to train the models. This is a dense cluster of servers, including its own Air Conditioning and temperature control. Depending on the operation mode and use of the cluster, the ventilators run at varying speeds, as the components tend to overheat. This causes variations in vibrations and sounds within the cluster that correlate with normal functioning. Additionally, we collected a dataset in collaboration with Chalmers University to evaluate the performance of cylindrical crushers using several proxies. This contribution was accepted to be presented at a conference in South Africa.

Complete architecture

The following block diagram in Figure 2 displays the architecture of the final system solution. It shows the different modules that make up the structure of the solution. It shows the parallelism between the audio-guided system (left side of the figure) and the vibration-guided system (right side); their structure will be the same, with the only difference being the type of recordings and the internal parameters of each system. The different modules that can be observed are: Data Acquisition, Data Processing, Storage (the figures representing data storage in the lower corners and the lower middle part of the image), Model Training, Model Evaluation, Alarm Generation (Monitor Alarm), and Real-time Integration (Integrated Decision and/or Model).

Figure 21 Block Diagram of the Final System Structure. To the left (blue) is the audio processing and evaluation, and to the right (green) is the vibration. Components in the central section (in orange) stand for the central functionalities.

The final version of the system includes the following hardware components:

Raspberry Pi 4 Model B (Pi4B). The Raspberry Pi is a high-performance microcomputer for embedded computing applications and IoT projects. This makes it ideal for the system to be developed. It has a Quad-core 64-bit ARM-Cortex A72 processor at 1.5 GHz, which provides the necessary processing power to handle the simultaneous tasks of collecting logs, signal processing and generating system alarms, as well as those necessary to manage its external connectivity, the command and control of its functions. This particular drive has a RAM of 4 GB, which allows it to handle the system workload. As for the interfaces, it has internet connectivity through the 802.11 b/g/n/ac Wireless LAN interface remotely and by cable through the Gigabit Ethernet port it incorporates. It also includes two USB2 ports and two USB3 ports. We used these for data collection and processing of the model using the aforementioned USB accelerator. This model has also been selected because of its low cost and low consumption, compared to traditional alternatives, which make it energy efficient for applications that require continuous operation.

Coral USB Accelerator. This peripheral device is designed to accelerate ML tasks using a specialised Edge TPU coprocessor, simply by plugging it into the USB port. The integrated Edge TPU coprocessor is a small Application-Specific Integrated Circuit (ASIC) designed by Google that accelerates TensorFlow Lite models in a power-efficient manner. It can perform 4 trillion operations per second (4 TOPS) using 2 Watts of power, i.e. 2 TOPS per Watt. In the context of the work, it speeds up inferences on the AI model to detect anomalies live in the final system. Being small, efficient and low-cost aligns with the work objectives mentioned.

Wit-motion accelerometer WT901c232. The WT901C232 is a multi-sensor device capable of detecting acceleration, angular velocity, angle (as a three-dimensional vector: roll, pitch and yaw) and magnetic field. Its compact design suits industrial and IoT applications like condition monitoring and predictive maintenance. The device configuration allows the user to address various use cases by interpreting the sensor data with intelligent algorithms, depending on the manufacturer. The scientific name of the sensor is AHRS IMU, a MEMS (micro-electro-mechanical systems) sensor. It is characterised by making measurements on all three axes concerning the sensor. This sensor captures vibrations by measuring acceleration in the three axes. It was chosen for this project due to its portability, low price, the precision it provides, and reported energy efficiency.

Microphone. The audio sensor uses a general-purpose microphone with a USB adapter to work on the Raspberry Pi. This device can be easily replaced with another with better acoustic properties, such as better frequency response, directivity, etc. These types of changes have a direct impact on the records collected and, therefore, on the developed system. Future studies of its impact on the final developed system may be considered for the final commercial solution and future versions.

Activities still to be performed:

The final HW installation could not be performed due to delays in the HW design of the data capturing device. The installation will be performed at the beginning of April 2025. The latter will not demand a lot of time neither resources. The objective is to have the device running at least a couple of months to have enough data to be processed before the end of the project.

2.7 BIM integration (Task 4.4)

2.7.1 General Summary

Building Information Modeling (BIM) activities for the CSI Mammendorf site focused on establishing a foundational digital representation of the quarry. APP Consultoría developed an accurate 3D topographic model of the site based on the drone flight documentation provided by WP1 partners. This model was created using standard BIM software and converted to the interoperable IFC format, providing a key baseline digital asset for the project and potential future BIM applications at the site.

2.7.2 Activities performed

Following the initial development phase reported in Deliverable D4.5, the primary activity regarding BIM for the CSI Mammendorf site involved ensuring the finalization and availability of the created 3D topographic model. The model, representing the quarry's terrain based on WP1 drone data, was prepared in the standard IFC format and made accessible for integration with other project platforms and potential future use by CSI.

3 Results

3.1 Data Logger and Raw Data Transmission and GPS connection

All needed data loggers have successfully been installed and connected to the CAN-BUS system in all (15) defined CSI machinery from three different OEMs. The logger proves to be reliable in the quarry environment and data transmission is reliable. The data logger is the base of the mobile data logging expert system developed and validated from DH&P and CSI in WP3 and WP6. The data transmission is built up and data is transmitted every few minutes to the AutoPLAN expert system for storage and normalisation. The data connection is reliable. The GPS connection in the quarry is sufficient in x and y-direction. The altitude data is only insufficient on the lower benches of the pit. Therefore, a RTK antenna installation was tested on the CAT 775G-3 dump truck and successfully approved.

3.2 Development of the KPIs

The basis for calculating the KPIs (or data outputs) is the recorded raw data (or data inputs) of the equipped machines. This data is, with exception of the weighting information of the mobile machines, available for all equipped machines. In accordance with the quarry needs and the KPIs defined in the GA the following target KPIs are defined (see Table 1). These KPIs are (if applicable for the machine) calculated for each machine individually. Algorithms for the calculation of a specific KPI can differ based on the available raw signals. From the individual KPIs global KPIs for the whole machinery fleet can easily be calculated (i.e. total fuel usage of the fleet, total fuel usage for overburden removal etc). However, as the first project targets are the individual machine KPIs as base for further calculations, the global plant KPIs are not listed in the following.

Table 1 Defined machine KPIs for the pilot Mammendorf

KPI	Description	Unit
Operational time	Total time the engine is running	h
Idle time	Time the engine is idling	h
Utilisation	Ratio of idling to operational time	%
Fuel usage total/average	Amount of fuel used in total and in average	ltr. and ltr./h
Fuel usage per activity	Total and average fuel used for activities (i.e. overburden removal, several machines)	ltr./h
Cycles Completed	Times driven between a source and a target geofence (i.e. mining bench to pre-crusher and back)	n
Tonnages produced of different materials	Material transported with differentiation between blasted hard rock, overburden, waste and product	t
Tonnages average	Average production of a machine per working time	t/h
Engine hours	Current engine hours readings of the machine	h
Warnings	Current warnings of machine	-
Tire pressure/temperature	Current pressure and temperature of tires	Bar/ °C
Distance driven (+ loaded)	Total distance driven, Total distance driven loaded	km
Maximum and average Speed	The maximum and average speed driven by the machine	km/h
Material tracking	Full material tracking with visualisation	-

Comments:

- Tire pressure and temperate signals are currently not available (see 2.4).
- Warnings are only partially available (on the Volvo truck assets). Mainly the OEMs do not send this data in the publicly defined J1939 format on the CAN bus. Here further external sensors injecting data into the bus can be evaluated in the future.
- Tonnage data from assets is also often not given by the OEMs in a readable format according to J1939 standard. Possible workarounds for calculations are external scales (e.g. Pfreundt), primary crusher scale data or a per asset defined fixed average value.
- KPIs can only be evaluated on assets where corresponding raw signals are available. Especially on older machines some signals are lacking.

The basic KPIs (used for almost all further analysis) are calculated and validated. This includes operational, idling and working times, distances and speeds and fuel consumption.

As an example for the calculated fuel consumption (l/h) for one day the results are as follows:

Figure 22 Calculated Fuel use (l/h) for a given day.

In comparison to the actual average fuel usage (l/h) documented in the pilot (see Figure 23) the fuel data are in a realistic range. The detailed use of the machine in different environments, operators and conditions needs to be longer monitored to develop a comprehensible KPI and see optimisation potential in the quarry operation.

Figure 23 Calculated fuel use (l/h) for a given day in relation to the actual average use documented by the pilot.

3.3 Material Tracking using the Geofences System

The 3D-geofence structure has been developed based on a new detailed survey of the quarry and a derived topographical model. An algorithm links the equipment position to the 3D-geofences (see example for the CAT dumper 775G in Figure 24) and in a further process the number of cycles between two geofences can be counted automatically (i.e. mining bench to pre-crusher and back to mining bench). Linked to the information of the weighing systems of the mobile machines the material will be tracked, and the mass flow can be visualised and analysed.

Component	Geofence	Uts (Start)	Uts (End)	Start	End	Duration [s]	Z min	Z max	Distance [m]	Average Speed [m/s]
Components	Dump Non Usable 80-118	179207813	179207815	18:11:53	18:11:55	2.0	49.130	49.220	0.0	0.0
Components	Mining Bench 60	179207816	179207818	18:12:04	18:12:08	2.8	48.220	48.880	2.4	3.4
Components	Dump Non Usable 80-118	179207819	179207821	18:12:11	18:12:11	0.0	48.270	48.820	8.2	14.9
Data	Mining Bench 50	179207832	179207838	18:12:12	18:12:18	6.0	48.830	48.180	8.2	8.7
Tracks	Dump Non Usable 80-118	179207839	179207845	18:12:19	18:12:19	0.0	48.590	50.540	1.3	32.0
Transfers	Mining Bench 50	179207847	179207851	18:12:27	18:12:31	4.0	49.760	50.360	11.2	11.6
GPS Import	Dump Non Usable 80-118	179207862	179207868	18:13:22	18:13:30	8.0	50.500	52.940	27.5	28.4
KPI Recalculation	Mining Bench 50	179207866	179207870	18:13:31	18:13:39	8.0	52.410	54.720	16.9	17.4
Geofence Update	Quarry Access Ramp unpaired	179207883	179207885	18:13:36	18:14:11	35.0	35.200	74.490	369.8	243.1
Geofence Update	Plant Road	179207892	179207894	18:14:12	18:15:09	57.0	74.680	114.870	356.5	427.3
Label	Plant Road	179207910	179207923	18:15:10	18:15:29	13.0	115.420	117.210	68.1	78.6
Label Categories	Plant Road	179207924	179207927	18:15:24	18:15:27	3.0	116.240	116.520	20.1	20.6
Label	Plant Road	179207928	179207932	18:15:28	18:15:32	4.0	116.640	116.940	39.2	41.4
Parameter	Plant Road	179207933	179207943	18:17:13	18:17:23	10.0	125.690	126.890	71.2	71.8
Parameter	Plant Road	179207944	179207948	18:17:24	18:17:28	4.0	129.430	129.820	13.5	13.5
Parameter	Plant Road	179207949	179207953	18:17:27	18:17:36	9.0	128.020	132.280	47.6	184.4
Parameter	Plant Road	179207959	179207969	18:18:09	18:18:19	10.0	125.920	126.560	14.6	15.1
Parameter	Plant Road	179207960	179208154	18:18:20	18:22:34	254.0	124.010	125.910	0.0	48.8
Parameter	Plant Road	179208055	179208062	18:22:35	18:22:42	7.0	126.270	128.190	11.7	12.1
Parameter	Plant Road	179208063	179208069	18:22:43	18:22:51	8.0	128.570	131.090	28.9	88.9
Parameter	Plant Road	179208094	179208196	18:23:14	18:23:16	2.0	128.860	129.230	13.5	13.5
Parameter	Plant Road	179208197	179208206	18:23:17	18:23:26	9.0	125.140	128.680	70.1	70.6
Parameter	Plant Road	179208207	179208213	18:23:27	18:23:33	6.0	123.990	125.990	44.8	46.8
Parameter	Plant Road	179208214	179208214	18:23:34	18:23:34	0.0	123.760	123.760	0.0	0.0
Parameter	Plant Road	179208215	179208277	18:23:35	18:24:37	62.0	115.230	123.520	344.0	434.7
Parameter	Quarry Access Ramp unpaired	179208278	179208278	18:24:38	18:24:38	0.0	115.230	115.230	0.0	0.0
Parameter	Quarry Access Ramp unpaired	179208279	179208283	18:24:39	18:24:43	4.0	75.360	114.680	397.7	434.4
Parameter	Quarry Access Ramp unpaired	179208284	179208286	18:25:44	18:26:26	42.0	55.320	75.240	87.3	212.0
Parameter	Mining Bench 50	179208287	179208292	18:26:27	18:26:32	5.0	51.820	54.700	26.1	20.9
Parameter	Dump Non Usable 80-118	179208293	179208300	18:26:33	18:26:40	7.0	50.220	51.840	21.0	21.4
Parameter	Mining Bench 50	179208301	179208306	18:26:41	18:26:46	5.0	49.310	50.110	14.4	14.3
Parameter	Dump Non Usable 80-118	179208307	179208322	18:26:47	18:27:02	15.0	48.920	49.460	4.1	19.9
Parameter	Mining Bench 50	179208323	179208330	18:27:03	18:27:10	7.0	49.090	49.210	6.9	8.2
Parameter	Dump Non Usable 80-118	179208331	179208334	18:27:11	18:28:14	63.0	48.960	50.170	3.6	28.4
Parameter	Mining Bench 50	179208335	179208347	18:28:15	18:28:17	2.0	48.820	50.130	5.3	5.3
Parameter	Dump Non Usable 80-118	179208348	179208358	18:28:18	18:28:28	10.0	50.290	52.000	13.0	13.2
Parameter	Mining Bench 60	179208359	179208363	18:28:29	18:28:33	4.0	52.190	54.840	21.8	18.3
Parameter	Mining Bench 60	179208364	179208374	18:28:34	18:29:07	33.0	55.430	74.810	87.0	209.4
Parameter	Quarry Access Ramp unpaired	179208375	179208384	18:29:08	18:30:04	56.0	75.040	114.290	355.7	423.3
Parameter	Quarry Access Ramp unpaired	179208385	179208385	18:30:05	18:30:05	0.0	115.260	115.260	0.0	0.0

Figure 24 Connection between the vehicle position and the 3D-geofences

4 Practical use of the AutoPLAN system at CSI

4.1 Regular Monitoring of the processes

CSI uses the 'AutoPLAN' system from DH&P to evaluate, analyse and optimise the actual use of mobile equipment in the quarry. The KPIs are regularly reviewed for this purpose. Over time, values emerge for all machines that are to be regarded as normal and therefore target values. If there are deviations from the normal values, CSI first uses the AutoPlan system to find the cause of the deviation. To do this, the machine is scrutinised more closely. For this purpose, the use of the machine is analysed in detail in the software. Parameters such as operating times, idle times and consumption are compared.

The map view is another useful tool for monitoring the efficiency of use. This is also used on a regular basis. Here, the movement profiles of individual or multiple machines can be viewed for freely definable periods of time. This allows conclusions to be drawn about the conditions under which the machines were working at the relevant time. Depending on the loading point and the material to be loaded, values such as consumption can vary considerably.

Figure 25 Different loading-conditions in the quarry - i.e. different weather conditions, that result in changing road conditions - can lead to differences in numbers.

Different machine configurations working together can also lead to deviations in the values of individual machines.

The movement data can be used to precisely analyse the loading locations and routes of the machines. This allows conclusions to be drawn as to whether operational specifications are being implemented and whether the operation is taking place as planned. Deviations in KPIs such as consumption, idle times or other relevant values can also be partially explained by analysing the map view. Reasons for deviating KPIs that can be explained in this way can be, for example

- difficult loading points
- Particularly long transport routes
- Particularly short transport routes
- Unfavourable meeting points that cause waiting times

1. too high or too low number of transport-equipment like dumpers or trucks

Especially the conditions of the transport routes play a particularly important role in the efficiency of the transport equipment. Excessive gradients lead to increased consumption and slow cycle times. Washouts caused by heavy rainfall, potholes or similar obstacles can increase the cycle times of the equipment. Stones lost by vehicles in front also lead to delays. This reduces the efficiency of the overall process. Specific and absolute consumption increases. Such changes can also be recognised in the map view.

Figure 26 Meeting-point with two trucks in the quarry. A key-point for efficient transport..

It is often possible to determine the probable cause of the deviating value after studying the data and maps in detail. If the problem still exists, the responsible personnel will be notified. Together with this person, the process is examined in reality. Here it is determined whether the assumption made based on the data can be confirmed.

Figure 27 Transferring the data to reality. Check of the situation in the quarry.

Then, if possible, the cause is eliminated to restore a smooth and efficient operation. This is done in close consultation with the supervising personnel and the construction machine operators. As a rule, they have to implement the changes and should be encouraged to avoid similar situations in the future. For this reason, past errors that have been identified during a data analysis are also communicated.

4.2 Identifying potential for improvement and optimising operating processes

In addition to day-to-day operations and optimisation, CSI uses AutoPLAN to optimise the efficiency of operational processes in general.

This makes it possible to check the machine configurations for optimum accuracy of fit. If changes in operational requirements mean that the combination of loader and transport equipment is no longer a good fit, the data can be used to analyse the situation. The influence of changes of a technical nature or in the operational organisation can also be demonstrated with the help of the data.

One example of this is the reduction in avoidable idle times of machinery. In the analyses of the daily processes of some mobile devices, it was determined that the proportion of avoidable idle time appears to be too high. A more detailed analysis of the data revealed that this is mainly due to coordinative processes. In this context, the machine operators were made aware of the resulting increases in emissions and costs. In particular, they were instructed to consistently switch off the machines during waiting times.

This may be useful and necessary in the following situations:

2. Waiting for the wheel loader in the return loading area for the next customer.
3. Waiting times for lorries in the return loading area.
4. Waiting times of dump trucks for oncoming traffic.
5. Plant downtimes.
6. Extended loading time of the excavators onto the dump trucks. These can be switched off in such cases.

...and much more.

Figure 26 shows how the idle times of a dump truck can be reduced through targeted training of the personnel using the data from the AutoPlan system. It can be seen that the hours of avoidable idling are significantly reduced during the test period. Compared to other days, this corresponds to a reduction of 80-90%.

In this case, AutoPlan was used directly to document the results and also to communicate with the drivers. This in turn led to a further learning effect. The usefulness of reducing idling was immediately recognisable for everyone involved.

Date	Time	Idle avoidable Hours [HH:mm:ss]	Date	Time	Idle avoidable Hours [HH:mm:ss]
1/13/2025	12:00 PM	0.5	1/14/2025	6:00 PM	0.1
1/13/2025	1:00 PM	0.1	1/14/2025	7:00 PM	0.4
1/13/2025	2:00 PM	0.4	1/14/2025	8:00 PM	0.5
1/13/2025	3:00 PM	0.3	1/14/2025	9:00 PM	0.3
1/13/2025	4:00 PM	0.1	1/14/2025	10:00 PM	
1/13/2025	5:00 PM	0.1	1/14/2025	11:00 PM	
1/13/2025	6:00 PM	0.0	1/15/2025	12:00 AM	
1/13/2025	7:00 PM	0.3	1/15/2025	1:00 AM	
1/13/2025	8:00 PM	0.4	1/15/2025	2:00 AM	
1/13/2025	9:00 PM	0.2	1/15/2025	3:00 AM	
1/13/2025	10:00 PM		1/15/2025	4:00 AM	
1/13/2025	11:00 PM		1/15/2025	5:00 AM	0.0
1/14/2025	12:00 AM		1/15/2025	6:00 AM	0.1
1/14/2025	1:00 AM		1/15/2025	7:00 AM	0.0
1/14/2025	2:00 AM		1/15/2025	8:00 AM	0.1
1/14/2025	3:00 AM		1/15/2025	9:00 AM	0.1
1/14/2025	4:00 AM		1/15/2025	10:00 AM	0.0
1/14/2025	5:00 AM	0.0	1/15/2025	11:00 AM	0.1
1/14/2025	6:00 AM	0.4	1/15/2025	12:00 PM	0.0
1/14/2025	7:00 AM	0.4	1/15/2025	1:00 PM	0.0
1/14/2025	8:00 AM	0.5	1/15/2025	2:00 PM	0.0
1/14/2025	9:00 AM	0.3	1/15/2025	3:00 PM	0.0
1/14/2025	10:00 AM	0.3	1/15/2025	4:00 PM	0.0
1/14/2025	11:00 AM	0.2	1/15/2025	5:00 PM	0.0
1/14/2025	12:00 PM	0.2	1/15/2025	6:00 PM	0.0
1/14/2025	1:00 PM	0.1	1/15/2025	7:00 PM	0.0
1/14/2025	2:00 PM	0.4	1/15/2025	8:00 PM	0.0
1/14/2025	3:00 PM	0.3	1/15/2025	9:00 PM	0.1
1/14/2025	4:00 PM	0.4	1/15/2025	10:00 PM	
1/14/2025	5:00 PM	0.4	1/15/2025	11:00 PM	

Figure 228 Comparison of Cat 775 G dump truck idle times

5 Impact assessment

As CSI has only worked actively with AutoPlan to date, the following impact assessment but also the conclusion in the next section focus on this application.

Most of the energy consumption within quarries derives from the use of mobile machinery. In the case of the pilot quarry of CSI the use of mobile machinery stands for 75% of total energy consumed (diesel consumption + total electricity consumption for stationary plant). Since the used electricity partly stems from CO₂ neutral sources (i.e. own photovoltaic plant but also percentages of the bought electricity) the percentage impact on the environment deriving from the usage of machinery running on fossil fuels is even higher. Furthermore usage of mobile equipment is one of the largest cost drivers in quarry operations, a significant improvement in cost efficiency is possible in this area. Hence targeting efficiency improvements of the employment of mobile machinery within quarries is not only a most promising approach to reduce energy consumption and environmental emissions of the quarry operations in total but may also result in significant cost improvements.

Here the AutoPlan system offers great potential. This already becomes clear after just a few months of using the software at the CSI quarry. Potentials for improvement in the area of mobile devices have already been identified. Even though the system is not yet complete and some data, such as mass movements, cannot be viewed so far, selective successes have already been achieved. The situation in open-cast mines such as the CSI quarry is constantly changing. This means that the open-cast mine management and the machine operators are faced with new challenges very often, if not every day. As a result, the processes, routes and machine constellations are constantly changing. As this happens simultaneously on a large, sometimes confusing site, the resulting losses in efficiency are difficult to control and to assess on site. Any inefficiencies that arise are therefore often difficult to recognise without considerable effort and are sometimes overseen in day-to-day business. If it is subsequently realised that something did not go well, for instance by analysing cost accounting or monthly financial statements it is rarely possible to determine exactly what the specific cause was and thus to derive improvement potential.

With the help of online data on the positions and efficiency values of the machines, it is possible to check whether the process is running efficiently and the machines are being used as intended in a timely manner and without considerable effort. If there are deviations from the relevant KPIs, the process can be scrutinised more closely in this way. In addition, once the causes have been eliminated, it is possible to clarify whether the operation is running smoothly again.

In principle, the system can be used in most quarry operations without any problems. The prerequisite is that the machines have modern data acquisition systems to be able to use the complete scope of target KPIs. As many companies use machines comparable to CSI, this possibility should exist. In addition, a data transfer option via WLAN or a mobile phone network must be available or be created.

It is important to realise that the AutoPlan system alone cannot improve efficiency. It is an analysis tool for management staff to scrutinise the process. The data obtained must be interpreted by the user and transferred to reality. From this, conclusions can be drawn from which measures can be derived. These in turn lead to changes and, where appropriate, an increase in efficiency.

6 Quarry Voices on Technology Deployment

The following section presents a structured interview conducted by ANEFA, as the coordinator of the DigiEcoQuarry project. The interview aimed to gather qualitative feedback from representatives of CSI concerning the technologies implemented at their site. The primary objectives included assessing overall perception, operational impacts, observed benefits, key success factors, potential barriers, and suggestions for future enhancements. Insights gained from this discussion provide valuable understanding regarding the effectiveness of technological innovations developed by the project, their replicability within the industry, and their alignment with broader sustainability goals.

1. Overall Perception

General assessment of implemented technologies:

CSI's main role as a pilot quarry focuses on analysing data from mobile equipment through internal sensors and external GPS systems. Despite early challenges, promising KPI results have been obtained since last autumn.

Added value to daily operations:

The technology significantly simplified the analysis of consumption and operation of mobile equipment, particularly highlighting the monitoring of idle times and other key metrics that can now be analysed more quickly and easily.

2. Key Benefits Observed

Operational efficiency: The ability to swiftly analyse processes related to mobile machinery from the desk has clearly enhanced productivity.

Environmental impact: Improved efficiency directly contributes to a significant reduction in energy consumption and associated emissions, enhancing the sustainability of operations.

Workplace safety: The technology did not have direct impact on workplace safety, but provided slight improvements in identifying road conditions.

Digitalisation: CSI emphasised the importance of digitalisation for informed decision-making, particularly regarding future investments in equipment, enabling rapid and effective comparisons among different options.

3. Success Factors and Adoption Potential

Ease of integration and user-friendliness: Currently, the system's interface is not yet fully user-friendly, but it already offers improved results compared to previous solutions, though it still requires some enhancements before broader adoption.

Replicability across different quarry sites: According to CSI, the system's replicability is high as it easily adapts to various types and brands of machinery commonly used in quarries.

Contribution to industry innovation: CSI confirmed that these technologies significantly contribute to industry innovation, particularly in optimising the energy consumption of mobile equipment.

Barriers to adoption: The main difficulty identified was extracting and translating data from diverse machinery into a coherent single system, along with potential issues regarding mobile connectivity and associated costs.

4. Future Outlook

Recommendations and opportunities for further optimisation: CSI recommends making the system more intuitive and user-friendly, incorporating configurable automated reports based on specific KPIs, and establishing proactive alerts for abnormal values or technical issues.

Long-term implementation prospects: CSI sees strong potential for extended long-term implementation once current challenges related to usability and data visualisation are resolved.

Alignment with the sector's sustainability goals: According to CSI, these technologies are definitely aligned with the sector's sustainability and net-zero emission goals, highlighting substantial potential to improve energy efficiency and resource optimization.

7 Conclusion and Future Recommendations

As stated above the development of mobile device data collection in the Mammendorf pilot is very promising. The system is in use and initial successes have been achieved in its application. It is planned to continue its use outside of the Diggiecoquarry project. The system facilitates the planning and monitoring of processes in open-cast mining. The use of energy-intensive and expensive machines can be monitored and optimised with the help of the tool. The quarry operation has thus been given a tool to reduce the frequency of errors, increase efficiency and improve availability. AutoPLAN can also be used to train employees on the equipment. For future strategic decisions, the analyses obtained can help to make the right decisions in terms of efficiency. It is to be expected that the consistent use of manufacturer-independent monitoring software such as AutoPLAN can significantly increase the overall effectiveness of a quarrying operation. This will result in a noticeable reduction in emissions, greenhouse gases and costs.

In order to ensure regular use of the system by the user in the future and to increase the saving effects achieved, we suggest the following:

Improvement of the user interface of the system. Not all individual values and analyses are currently accessible to the user. In addition, operation is not yet intuitive enough. The more user-friendly the system is, the more it will be accepted and used by quarry personnel.

Complex key figures should be developed from the 'simple' KPIs obtained so far. These will make it easier to define a target status and recognise deviations at a glance. Also the communication between the systems of different machines could be evaluated.

The option of receiving automated reports on certain KPIs should be developed. This greatly facilitates the daily monitoring of processes and also the usage of KPIs in monthly reporting and in management systems.

It should be possible to define warning thresholds for deviations from target values. Automated warnings can be generated from this. In this way, it is possible to react promptly to problems during operation without actively opening the software.

Technical error messages, which are already available in the machine control system, should be transmitted directly to the user via AutoPlan. This could help to increase availability and avoid consequential damage.

The connection to other, potentially available, digitally connected systems of the quarry should be optimised. Examples of this are mining planning or plant control.

Currently, only some CAN-Bus values from the internal machine control systems are freely released by the machinery manufacturers for independent analyses. The rest of the needed values have to be encrypted, programmed manually and then be evaluated to generate usable machinery data. Since each quarry uses different machinery from different OEMs and also of different generations and each machine data read out has to be programmed individually, the costs of installing and setting-up such a system in a quarry largely depends on the amount of freely accessible data. Although this project proves that it is generally possible to identify and extract data which is not freely released by the OEMs work should be done to improve this situation - if necessary with political or regulatory pressure. Standardization in this field would help a lot in decreasing effort and costs to install such systems, which will eventually lead to a broader potential customer base and thus more efficiency increases.

As tire-pressure is a very important factor to operate a machine in a safe and efficient way, it was planned to connect the installed TPMS-systems to the data-logger and transfer the data to the platform. However, numerous attempts to contact the manufacturer and harmonise the interfaces have failed. As a result, it has not yet been possible to save this sensor data in the data logger and make it available in the system. For the future it should be made possible to integrate such data in this system. If new TPMS are bought the question of potential interfaces to a third party software system such as AutoPlan must be considered as a prerequisite for the buying decision. This also holds for procurement of other third party installations such as external weight scales, or GPS-systems.

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